

IPBES VA Chapter 2. Literature review on multiple values concepts in academic literature / IPBES values assessment (2.11)

Code: IPBES_VA_2.11

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Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES values assessment. To respond to mandate that the IPBES Scoping document for the values assessment has for Chapter 2, regarding the assessment of “the coverage of diverse conceptualizations of values with regard to nature and nature’s benefits to people”, this literature review was done to provide an overview of temporal and thematic trends regarding the use of multiple value concepts in the academic literature. This part of the literature review in the strategy chapter 2 has used is described as stage 3 in section 2.1.3.

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic review for articles indexed in Scopus from 2005 to December 2019
- **Search languages:** Title/abstract in English
- **Search engine:** Scopus
- **Exact search date:** 12th December 2019
- **Search terms:**

```
TS = (
  TITLE-ABS-KEY (
    (
      (valu* OR wellbeing OR well-being OR "quality of life") AND (nature
      OR ecosystem OR biodiversity OR landscape) OR
      "environmental valu*" OR
      "human-nature relat*" OR
      "society nature relat*"
    ) AND
    PUBYEAR > 2004 AND
    SUBJAREA (
      ARTS OR
      BUSI OR
      DECI OR
      ECON OR
      PSYC OR
      SOCI OR
      ENVI OR
      EARTH OR
      MULT OR
      AGRI OR
      Undefined
    )
  )
```

- **Sample extracted:** 148,082 records
- **Fields extracted (A):**
 - Authors,
 - Author(s) ID,
 - Title,
 - Year,
 - Source title,
 - Volume,
 - Issue,
 - Cited by,
 - DOI,
 - Link,
 - Affiliations,
 - Authors with affiliations,
 - Abstract,
 - Author Keywords,
 - Index Keywords,
 - Document Type,
 - Publication Stage,
 - Access Type,
- **Location and format of the data (A):** IPBES_VA_2.11_12-2019_(A).csv

Treatment applied: The 148,082 abstracts **(A)** were processed by using artificial intelligence procedure in the R library STM (Roberts, 2013) **(R1)** to obtain a preliminary topic model. Data processing included word stemming, punctuation removal, stop word removal, etc. Initially, 40 topics were modelled. Eight exemplar abstracts were extracted from each of the 40 topics **(B)**.

- **Sample extracted:** 40 topics
- **Location and format of the data (B):** IPBES_VA_2.11_06-2020_(B).csv

Treatment applied: Three coders manually interpreted the meaning of each topic – semantically inferring what category each topic referred to by reading the top abstract in each topic and the most diagnostic words in each topic. This analysis was intended to screen and determine eligibility, based on relevance to the aims of chapter 2, on a three-point scale (*not all relevant, somewhat relevant, very relevant*). If two of the three coders found a topic to be either *somewhat* or *very relevant*, it was included in the assessment. Topics that were categorised by at least 2 coders as irrelevant were removed. These identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion steps resulted in a final analytic dataset of n=40,133.

- **Sample extracted:** 40,133 records

Treatment applied: The 40,133 records went through a second process of AI topic modelling algorithm **(R1)**, testing two models: 40 and 60 topics. The 60-topic model produced more detailed topics and was chosen for better conduct qualitative analysis of thematic trends **(C)**. To interpret thematic content, the coding exercise was repeated, selecting eight exemplars per topic and coding them for relevance. As in the first stage of analysis, if two coders categorised a topic as *somewhat* or *very relevant*, it was kept within the final analytic dataset. Applied to the 60 topics modelled, this process produced a final classification with 46 relevant topics.

- **Sample extracted:** 46 relevant topics
- **Location and format of the data (C):** IPBES_VA_2.11_07-2020_(C).csv

Treatment applied: The 46 relevant topics were classified as per their relationship to IPBES’s broad disciplinary categories to valuing nature: Biophysical, Economic, Health, Socio-cultural and ILK **(D)**.

- **Location and format of the data (D):** IPBES_VA_2.11_07-2020_(D).csv

Treatment applied: The 46 relevant topics **(C)** were analysed through descriptive statistics to find temporal trends in the literature and the main words in each topic are presented in files **(V1), (V2), (V3), (V4), and (V5)**.

Treatment applied: Qualitative analyses were performed to understand the meaning of the research topics and the relations among them (network analysis). The report of these analyses can be found in **(E)**.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_2.11_12-2019_(A)	csv	450 MB	Database with 148,082 records obtained from the search in Scopus

B	IPBES_VA_2.11_06-2020_(B)	csv	508 KB	40 topics modelled through (R1), based on (A), with 8 exemplars each for manual interpretation
C	IPBES_VA_2.11_07-2020_(C)	csv	790 KB	60 topics modelled through (R1), based on 40,133 records, with 8 exemplars each for manual interpretation
D	IPBES_VA_2.11_07-2020_(D)	csv	2 KB	Classification of 46 relevant topics per their relationship to IPBES's broad disciplinary categories to valuing nature
E	IPBES_VA_2.11_10-2020_(E)	pdf	616 KB	Report of qualitative analyses and results
R1	IPBES_VA_2.11_05-2020_(R1)	txt	3 KB	Artificial intelligence procedure in the R library STM
V1	IPBES_VA_2.11_10-2020_(V1)	mp4	5 MB	Main words in biophysical topics
V2	IPBES_VA_2.11_10-2020_(V2)	mp4	478 KB	Main words in economic topics
V3	IPBES_VA_2.11_10-2020_(V3)	mp4	945 KB	Main words in socio topics
V4	IPBES_VA_2.11_10-2020_(V4)	mp4	162 KB	Main words in ILK topics
V5	IPBES_VA_2.11_10-2020_(V5)	mp4	954 KB	Main words in other topics